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WWRF Connected Vehicles Report

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WWRF VIP CV WG ACTIVITIES

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- WWRF VIP CV liaison activity with ITU-T CITS is ongoing; an update regarding VIP CV activity was presented at ITU-T CITS meeting on MARCH 17, 2023.
- A second white paper on connected vehicles is under way and is planned for completion by end of April.

WWRF VIP CV WG ACTIVITIES

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- A special issue of Wireless Personal Communications journal is scheduled for publication in the third quarter consisting of selected papers from IEEE ANTS 2022.
- A proposal is being developed for a third white paper on connected vehicles concerning the impact of 6G on Connected Vehicles
- A Connected Vehicles panel was organized, partially sponsored by WWRF, on December 20, 2022 at 2022 IEEE ANTS.

Panel at IEEE ANTS 2022

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IEEE International Conference on Advanced Networks and Telecommunications Systems

18-21 December 2022 // Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India

Scalable, Secure, and Sustainable Connectivity for All

Panel on AI/Machine Learning-Enabled (CAV) in the Era of 5G, 6G, and Beyond

Sponsored by Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF)

Panel Chair and Panelists

Dr. Seshadri Mohan, University of Arkansas at Little Rock, sxmohan@ualr.edu

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Klaus David, University of Kassel, Germany, david@uni-kassel.de

Dr. Burak Kantarci, University of Ottawa, ON, Canada, Burak.Kantarci@uottawa.ca

Dr. Bhavani Shankar, University of Luxemborg, Bhavani.Shankar@uni.lu
(<mailto:Bhavani.Shankar@uni.lu>)

Dr. Pradipta Biswas, IISc, pradipta@iisc.ac.in

WWRF 49 VIP CV Panel on
AI/ML-assisted connected and
autonomous vehicles for 6G and
beyond, March 28, PUT, Poznan

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- PANEL CHAIR: Seshadri Mohan, Professor, UA Little Rock, USA
- Pradipta Biswas, Associate Professor, IISc Bangalore, India
- Merouane Debbah, Professor, Chief Researcher AI and Digital Science Research Center (AIDRC), Technology Innovation Institute, Abu Dhabi
- Ravi Puvvala, Vice President of Strategic Partnerships, Harman International; founder and CEO of Savari
- Bhavani Shankar, Research Scientist at SnT, University of Luxembourg.
- Sachin Sharma, Professor, Associate Dean, International Affairs, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Graphic Era Deemed to be University, Dehradun, India

WWRF Huddle

Singapore

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- A CV Workshop is planned for May 8, 2023 in Singapore.
- Five speakers have confirmed their participation and, possibly, one or two more are expected to confirm.

